

Summation of multiple times of a geometric series and its binomial series

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Abstract: This paper presents a binomial series of summation of multiple times of a geometric series. This will be useful for the researchers who are involving to solve the scientific problems.

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Summation of multiple times of a geometric series:

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad (1)$$

The left side of Equ.(1) is the summation of multiple times of a geometric series[1-5] and the right side of Equ.(1) is a binomial series derived from the computation of multiple times of a geometric series. Here, the optimized combination [1-5] is shown below:

$$V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\cdots(r+n)}{n!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+r)}{r!} = V_n^r,$$

$$i.e., \quad V_r^n = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{r+i}{n!} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{n+i}{r!} = V_n^r \quad (n, r \in N),$$

where $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, V_r^n is a binomial coefficient, and $n!$ is the factorial of n .

Some results [1, 2] of the optimized combination are provided below:

i). $V_n^0 = V_0^n = 1 \quad (n \geq 1 \quad \& \quad n \in N),$

where V_n^0 always implies V_0^n , *i.e.*, $V_n^0 \Rightarrow V_0^n$.

Note that $V_r^n = V_n^r = (n+r)C_r = (n+r)C_n = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!}$ and $V_0^0 = 1$.

ii). $V_r^n = V_n^r \quad (n, r \geq 1 \quad \& \quad n, r \in N) \quad \& \quad V_n^0 = V_0^n.$

When substituting $r = 1$, Equ. (1) becomes the summation of two times of a geometric series,

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n x^{i_2} = \sum_{i_2=0}^n x^{i_2} + \sum_{i_2=1}^n x^{i_2} + \sum_{i_2=2}^n x^{i_2} + \dots + \sum_{i_2=n}^n x^{i_2} = 1 + 2x + 3x^2 + \dots + (n+1)x^n.$$

$$1 + 2x + 3x^2 + \dots + (n+1)x^n = \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1)x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^1 x^i.$$

When substituting $r = 2$, Equ. (1) becomes the summation of three times of a geometric series,

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} = \sum_{i_2=0}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} + \sum_{i_2=1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} + \sum_{i_2=2}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} + \dots + \sum_{i_2=n}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n x^{i_3} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^2 x^i.$$

Similarly, if the above process continues upto r times, the r^{th} equation becomes as follows:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i = \sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \dots \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} \quad (2)$$

If substituting $r = 0$, Equ. (2) becomes the actual geometric series,

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^0 x^i = \sum_{i_1=0}^n x^{i_1} = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots + x^n \quad (\because V_0^0 = V_i^0 = v_0^i = 1, i \in N).$$

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